

HARNESSING PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL TO AUGMENT EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN THE MICRO-FINANCE SME SECTOR

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ABSTRACT: The study sought to establish the effect of psychological capital on employee engagement on small to medium scale micro finance institutions. Secondary objectives were developed using psychological capital constructs namely hope, self-efficacy and resilience. The study adopted a quantitative approach backed by positivist philosophy. A sample of 350 respondents was determined using the Yamane's model. Stratified random sampling was adopted and data was collected using a structured questionnaire. The results of the study indicate that psychological capital has a significant effect on employee engagement. The study recommends that employee behavioral workshops, mentorship, ethical leadership and coaching programmes directed at developing psychological capital in SMEs.

KEY WORDS: psychological capital, employee engagement, SME, Hope, Self-efficacy and Resilience

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee engagement may not be a new phenomenon but its consequences in business has been highly pronounced in recent years. It is universally agreed that employee engagement is a prominent factor in inducing the business bottom line (Muparangi et al. 2021). Employee engagement yields significant results for an organisation if carefully exploited. Erbası & Ozbek (2017) indicates that engaged employees are 17% more productive. Furthermore, engaged workforce pays attention to every detail of their tasks and have zeal, thus do not easily give up even when faced with challenges. This leads to innovation which further influences high performance and high-quality goods and services. Once quality is attained, customer base is bound to escalate, thus increasing profits for the organisation and induce the business bottom line.

Amunkete and Rothmann (2015) avers that companies with high levels of employee engagement are seen as the best to work for because people are seen to be prioritised before the needs of the organization. Thus, employee engagement plays a pivotal role in the image of any organization leading to competitive advantage.

In Zimbabwe, SMEs have been failing in terms of employee productivity as well as capacity utilisation. While there are many factors contributing to this dismal performance, employee engagement cannot be ruled out as one of the reasons for this poor showing. Confederation of Zimbabwe Industries (CZI) survey in (2000) revealed that the declining of the Microfinance sector is not a surprise but rather as a result of disengaged workforce and turnover rates (Avolio, 2007). Furthermore, Erbası & Ozbek (2017) reported that in a survey carried out in USA and Canada, disengaged employees are ten 10 times likely to quit their jobs within a year. Harunavamwe (2018) noted SMEs face dilemma in coming up with employee engagement strategies as they lack financial resources. There is need to establish if SMEs can harness psychological capital for performance.

In formal institutions, psychological capital has been flaunted as one of the solutions to employee engagement. However, this remains to be tested in SMEs with regards to micro-finance

sector. It is therefore important for the study to be carried out in this sector as given its importance in poverty alleviation as well as economic growth. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the effect of psychological capital on employee engagement in the Microfinance SME sector with a special reference to micro finance institutions in Bulawayo metropolitan province.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Employee Engagement

Employee engagement has attracted many scholars since its introduction. Despite this, there is little academic literature on the matter, and rather little is known about how to persuade employee engagement. A cloud of confusion still looms around the term employee engagement even after numerous attempts by researchers to clearly define it. Çavuş and Gökçen (2015) state there is no all-rounder approach to the definition of employee engagement, hence it depends on the sector or company trying to define the term. Kahn (1990) defines employee engagement as the presence of emotional, physical and cognitive capabilities in an employee. On the other hand, Macey and Schneider (2008) indicate that employee engagement is in three parts which are psychology, behaviour and traits. Cheung (2011) protested that if employee engagement is broken into three parts, it won't be effective in terms employee's assertiveness towards their work. Makowski-Komura and Bebenroth (2020) discovered that job satisfaction is heavily affected by Motivational cultural intelligence which is closely linked to psychological issues as explained by the socio-cultural psychology.

2.2. Psychological capital

Luthans and Youssef (2007) highlight that psychological capital is the development of an individual's positive mental state through hope, optimism, resilience and self-efficacy. Stajkovic and Luthans (1998) indicate that psychological capital is one's positive evaluation of a situation and likelihood of achieving a targeted goal based on self-motivation and endurance. Thus, psychological capital is a multi-dimensional concept revealed by four components namely hope, efficacy, resilience and optimism (Luthans and Youssef, 2007).

As stated above in the definition, psychological capital can be developed in individuals. Luthans and Youssef (2007) discovered that psychological capital is developable because it is made up of states not personality or qualities which are inherent. Thus, these can be taught and developed over time. Stajkovic and Luthans (1998) further states that psychological capital can be established through a series of observations in the present and applied in the future. Luthans and Youssef (2007) suggest that organizations can use psychological capital to their own advantage.

Stajkovic and Luthans (1998) urges that this newly found branch of psychology does not substitute psychology but rather compliments it. The branch emphasizes in focusing on the positive side of things rather than the negative. However, it does not totally ignore the wrong, but rather gives emphasis to the right. There is a possibility that emphasizing on what goes wrong may end up in a half solution or rather none at all (Stajkovic and Luthans 1998). This may affect an employee's well-being at work.

2.3. Dimensions of psychological capital

Research indicates that there are four main components of psychological capital. Luthans and Youssef (2007) and Pillay et al (2009) all agree that psychological capital has four main components namely hope, efficacy, resilience and optimism. Recently the four dimensions have been shortened to an acronym H.E.R.O.

2.3.1. Hope

Goal achievement can prove to be an impossible task in some instances. Individuals need agency and hope to attain goals. Hence provide self-rallied motivation to achieve goals. Therefore, hope is a motivational tool which may be used to achieve a given target. Durrah et al (2016) viewed hope as a motivational state resulting from achievement focused drive. Cavus and Gokcen (2015) add on to say, hope supports positive feelings and fuel the notion that dreams come true.

Numerous studies have pointed out that hope is an indicator of high performance, work satisfaction and motivation to cope with stressful circumstances (Cavus and Gokcen, 2015). Hopeful individuals are most likely to craft goals that are challenging and provide themselves with motivation and direction. If one feels defeated, they tend to feel exposed and cannot control the situation. In such circumstances, hopeful individuals are most likely to bounce back. Peterson et al. (2009) discovered that individuals who are hopeful are engaged. Hope in any workplace can be an important source of engagement.

Harunavamwe (2018) conducted a study to establish the impact of psychological capital on engagement of banking sector employees in South Africa. The study revealed that hopeful employees have positive attitude towards goal accomplishment. In the same study, hope was discovered to be the biggest contributor among psychological constructs. These conclusions parallel the findings of Tabaziba (2015) whose study was a cross-sectional study of Zimbabwe and South Africa. Hope was found to be a significant factor in employee engagement. Hopeful employees would thrive in economic difficulties hoping things will turn around. In a bid to establish the impact of psychological capital, Kapusuz and Çavuş (2019) found that in Turkey hope was the predictor of employee engagement.

Gustitia (2019) study in Indonesia focused on 82 generation employees and hope was found to be playing a significant role also. However, it must be noted that these studies focused on established organisations and it remains to be seen if the same

applies in SMEs. Studies of hope have been carried out in other countries like South Africa, Italy and many others and proved to be an important source of positive psychology and engagement. However, as indicated above these studies were carried out on established, large organizations and developed countries. Hence this research seeks to establish if hope has similar effect on engagement under a subdued economic environment in a third world /developing country.

2.3.2. Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is based on Bandura's social cognitive theory. He defined self-efficacy as one's ability to establish ways to perform certain task so as to attain a goal. Furthermore, Bandura (2001) states that individuals with self-efficacy perceive adversaries as manageable given adequate skills and determination. In the business arena Luthans and Stajkovic, (1998) defined self-efficacy as the conviction or general belief by an individual about their capabilities to rally motivation, internal resources and course of action needed to execute a certain task. In general, it is an individual's ability to motivate and believe in them that they can achieve self-imposed goals or imposed goals. Cavus and Gokcen (2015) state that self-efficacy stimulates self-motivation in positive and negative sides. Hence, results in acting beyond actual abilities and attain the desired goal.

Iddagoda and Opatha (2017) postulated that self-efficacy is not linked to one's competences but it is highly linked to one's belief in their personal competences. Individuals who have high levels of self-efficacy make a pathway to achieve goals through the internal agent that control them. Several studies which have been carried out to establish the impact self- efficacy indicate that there is a positive relationship between self-efficacy and performance output (Judge et al., 2007). Stojkovic (2013) determined that there is a correlation between self-efficacy and performance and job satisfaction. Through these studies, it can be established that there is a positive relationship between self-efficacy and employee engagement since performance and satisfaction are positive indicators of employee engagement.

Self-efficacy has been touted as one of the factors behind improved efficiency in organisations. However, there is little evidence of its impact on employee engagement. Kaplan and Biçkes (2003)'s study on the manufacturing sector in South Africa discovered that employees with high degree of self-efficacy are committed to their work. Ground breaking the impact of psychological capital, Harunavamwe (2018) discovered that banking sector employees in South Africa with self-confidence are likely to contribute more towards attainment of organisational goals. This was also supported by Kapusuz and Cavus (2019) study in Turkey where public sector employees were found to be more engaged due to self-confidence. Erbas and Ozbek, (2016) study in Turkey also confirms these results. However, the study was carried out on a single organisation thus affecting generalization. In this study, researchers seek to establish if self-confidence has an impact on engagement of employees in a pandemic riddled environment.

2.3.3. Resilience

Resilience is the positive response in hard times or experiences (Masten and Reed, 2002). Luthans (2002) defined resilience as the developable ability to recover from failure or disappointment. Cavus and Gokcen (2015) determined that resilience responds to personality that in turn affect people to adapt to situations that they may face in life. Abbas et al. (2014) states that resilience is used as catalyst to achieve goal as it helps to adjust to change. Harunavamwe (2018) suggests that resilient

people easily accept the changes in their surroundings hence less likely to resist change. Coutu (2002) states that resilience is characterized by a clear view of the problem or situation which in turn encourages emotional balance. Therefore, individuals with high levels of resilience can easily improvise. Furthermore, challenges faced by individuals who possess resilience are seen as a stepping stone to greater heights and arouse motivation to keep going. Previous research has indicated that individuals who possess resilience are most likely to cope under stressful circumstances as they show Myra's big five personality traits namely Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism. This in turn helps the member to cope with changes in their surroundings. Avolio et al. (2007) urge that a positive relationship exists between workplace happiness, commitment and employee engagement. Thus, previous research indicates that resilience and employee engagement are joined like head and neck. It remains to be seen if the same applies to SMEs as previous research mainly focused on formal organizations.

Resilience can be viewed as a coping mechanism in modern turbulent environments for human capital and the organization as a whole. Modern organizations are characterized by high turbulence and one can say in such times change is inevitable. Change such as retrenchment, restructuring and relocation are

the new black in modern organizations. Research has proven beyond doubt that these changes have negative effect on employees (Paeka, Schuckert, Kimc & Lee, 2015). This may result in a stressed work force and no engagement at all. However, resilience helps people to bounce back even after a bad experience or failure. Therefore, it is arguable to say resilience is important in modern day organizations especially those that are not fully developed like SMEs.

Resilience measures resistance in face of adversity. In a study conducted in South Africa by Harunavamwe (2018), majority of engaged banking sector employees were resilient. This indicated that resilient is positively related to employee engagement. Supporting Harunavamwe (2018)'s findings, Tabaziba (2015) discovered that resilient employees in South Africa would stay and support the organization despite problems. However, Kapusuz and Cavus (2019) study in Turkey indicate weaker relationship between resilience and employee engagement. There is need to establish the relationship between resilience and employee engagement with a special focus on SMEs operating in a subdued environment.

2.4. Research Model

Figure 1 below shows research model for this study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The model has been developed taking into account key constructs of independent variable (Hope, Self-efficacy and Resilience) and dependent variable Employee engagement.

2.5. Hypotheses

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between hope and employee engagement in the SME sector.

H2: There is a significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and employee engagement the SME sector.

H3: There is a significant positive relationship between resilience and employee engagement in the SME sector.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study is based on positivist philosophy as it seeks to establish causal relationship between psychological capital and employee engagement (Muparangi & Makudza, 2020). A quantitative strategy was adopted in a bid to be as objective and factual as possible. Cross-sectional research design was used as the main plan of the study since. The study targeted 400 employees from small to medium micro finance firms in Bulawayo Zimbabwe. A sample of 350 respondents was calculated using Yamane model of sample determination. Data was collected from selected SMEs using structured questionnaire and 75% response rate was achieved. AMOS

software was used for data analysis through applications such as structural equation modelling.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Demographic profile

In terms of gender 60% of respondents were males while 40% were females. The results also indicate that 7.5% of respondents were aged below 20 years, 42.5% were 20 to 29 years, 35% were aged 30-39 years and 15% were above 40 years. This may be attributed to the fact that SMEs are a source of employment in Zimbabwe than any other sector. In terms of education, 42.5% respondents were advanced level certificates holders followed by 27.5% ordinary level certificate holders. Further to that, 17.5% of the respondents were diploma holders while 12.5% were degree holders. Results also indicate that 47.5 % of the employees had served as employees for less than a year while 25% had served for 1-4 years, 20% served for 5-9 years and 7.5% were above 10 years.

4.2. Convergent validity

Prior to hypothesis testing, data were subjected to convergent and discriminatory validity tests. Model fit Indices, Composite reliability, average variance extracted (AVE) and standardised factor loadings were used to determine convergent validity. Table 1 below illustrates results of convergent validity.

Table 1. Convergent validity and Discriminant validity.

Latent Variable	Indicator Variable	Standardized Loadings	Composite Reliability	Ave	Square root of Ave/DV
Hope	H1	0.981***	0.97	0.9693	0.98453
	H2	0.983***			
	H3	0.994***			
	H4	0.993***			
	H5	0.987***			
	H6	0.971***			
Resilience	R1	0.982***	0.96	0.9785	0.989192
	R2	0.999***			
	R3	0.978***			
	R4	0.985***			
	R5	0.992***			
	R6	0.977***			
Self-Efficacy	SE1	0.984***	0.95	0.9825	0.991211
	SE2	0.982***			
	SE3	0.996***			
	SE4	0.999***			
	SE5	0.998***			
	SE6	0.988***			
Engagement	EE1	0.997***	0.97	0.9427	0.970927
	EE2	0.997***			
	EE3	0.993***			
	EE4	0.972***			
	EE5	0.958***			
	EE6	0.977***			
Note: ***Significant at $p < 0.001$					

The model fit indices proves that there was convergent validity as all the indices fell within the acceptable range as per (Makanyeza & Chikazhe 2017) ($\chi^2/df= 1.850$, GFI = 0.912, AGFI = 0.905, NFI =0.932, TLI = 0.935, CFI =0.943, RMSEA = 0.039). Results indicate that that convergence validity exists with all indicator variables converging to measure latent variables. AVE for convergent validity were over 0.50 thus indicating that there is convergent validity (Makanyeza & Chikazhe 2017). Composite reliability statistics for all the constructs are above the minimum threshold of 0.7 (Muparangi et al, 2021). Standardised factor loadings were significant at $p < 0.001$.

4.3. Discriminant validity

To assess discriminate validity, inter construct correlations are compared with Squared AVE. Results indicate that there is

discriminant validity since squared AVE are greater than inter construct correlation (Makanyeza & Chikazhe 2017).

4.4. The structural model

To test the proposed structural model, Structural equation modelling was employed in AMOS. Path Analysis figure 2 illustrate results of the SEM for hypotheses H1 –H3. The structural model shows that the model fit ($\chi^2/df= 1.874$, GFI = 0.919, AGFI = 0.901, NFI =0.951, TLI = 0.940, CFI =0.956, RMSEA = 0.041). Results indicate that there is a significant relationship between hope, resilience, self-efficacy and the dependent variable employee engagement. Table 2 below shows beta coefficients of individual constructs as they relate to employee with employee engagement.

Table 2. Convergent validity and Discriminant validity

				Estimate	SE	R	P	Comment
H ₁	Engagement	<---	Hope	0.449	.419	0.671	***	Supported
H ₂	Engagement	<---	Efficacy	0.234	.311	0.534	***	Supported
H ₃	Engagement	<---	Resilience	0.309	.319	0.587	***	Supported
Note: ***Significant at $p < 0.001$								

Figure 2. Structural Model

4.5. Discussion and theoretical implications

Hypothesis 1 (H₁) predicted that there is a significant positive relationship between hope and employee engagement. H₁ is accepted with ($\beta = 0.449$, $P = 0.00$, $r = 0.419$). Results indicate there is a significant positive relationship between hope and employee engagement. Hopeful employees are likely to be committed to an organisation.

Dawkins (2014) identified hope as one of the key constructs of psychological capital. Basing on results it can be concluded that hope plays a pivotal role in employee engagement. Employees with low levels of engagement also indicated low levels of hope. The findings correspond well with Harunanvamwe (2018) and Yavas et al. (2013) who discovered that hopeful employees pursue strategies to reach their goals by feeling energetic, enthusiastic and being happily immersed in their work. They dedicatedly and energetically work towards their goal and task achievement.

Hypothesis 2 (H₂) claim that there is a significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and employee engagement. H₂ is accepted ($\beta = 0.234$, $P = 0.00$, $r = 0.434$). Thus, employees who have self-confidence are more likely to be engaged to their organisation. Psychological capital is an individual's positive mental state which includes self-confidence Luthans et al. (2007). Thus the underlying objective was to determine the value of self-confidence. Literature review concluded that self-efficacy is a stimuli self-motivation in positive and negative sides, hence result in acting beyond actual abilities and attain the desired goal. From results it can be concluded that employees who lack confidence are less engaged. Results indicate a strong relationship between self-confidence and employee engagement. However previous researchers have divergent findings. Davids (2011) contradicts this suggesting that only a moderate percentage of the variation in employee engagement is explained by self-efficacy.

Hypothesis 3 (H₃) predicted that there is a significant relationship between resilience and employee

engagement. H₃ is accepted ($\beta = 0.309$, $P = 0.00$, $r = 0.587$). The result mean that resilient employees are more likely to be engaged to their organisation. Avolio et al. (2007) and (Youssef & Luthans, 2007) urge that a positive relationship exists between workplace happiness, commitment and employee engagement. The study discovered that resilience plays an important role in levels of employee engagement. A resilient employee does not give up easily even after facing challenges. They have the willpower and easily accept their surroundings changes hence they are less likely to resist change (Harunavamwe, 2018). Present study results are in sync with Tabaziba (2015)'s findings where resilient employees in South Africa would stay and support the organization despite problems. Abbas et al (2014) discovered that resilient employees use challenges as a springboard to reach for higher ground, hence they keep engaged. However, on the contrary Kapusuz and Cavus (2019)'s study in Turkey indicated a weaker relationship between resilience and employee engagement.

4.6. Practical implications

In the present study, hope, resilience and self-efficacy play a pivotal role in engaging employees. Therefore, the study recommends that organisations seeking to enhance employee engagement can incorporate and develop personal resources.

Based on the findings, hope is the highest predictor of employee engagement. It is therefore recommendable that when SMEs are developing the psychological capacities as a way to boost work engagement, much focus should be on developing the hope component. This can be achieved by setting clear, practical, and challenging goals. Victories of small targets can increase the hope of achieving the ultimate goal (Guangyi & Shanshan, 2016). Therefore, management can enhance engagement by coaching employees on setting goals, developing career plans and giving timely feedback (Barkhuizen & Rothmann, 2006).

Management needs to develop positive work emotions as soon as an employee is hired. They should be put through intensive training of developing psychological

capital. Workshops, coaching and mentorship programs must be put in place. In addition, it is sensible to use practical interviews when hiring rather than the old fashioned way of interviews. From practical interviews management can easily identify if employees demonstrate resilience and possess hope or self-efficacy.

4.7. Limitations of the study

While the study was vital in unlocking the necessity of psychological capital for employee engagement in the SME sector, it had some limitations. The study was basically quantitative in nature shunning out qualitative issues. Further to that the study focussed on SMEs in the micro finance sector and as such it may not be generalised to other sectors.

4.8. Directions for future research

Future studies may consider investigate the impact of psychological capital incorporating qualitative issues in the process. Further to the that there is need to consider how psychological capital impact employee engagement in other SME sectors as well as informal SME sector.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, SMEs who lack financial resources to stimulate engagement of their employees can heavily rely on psychological capital which has been discovered to be playing a crucial role in improving employee engagement. Hope, self-efficacy and resilience can affect employee's commitment to the organisation. The onus is on the organisation to create an environment which can stimulate self-efficacy, resilience and hope.

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